

THE ROLE OF THE INTERNET IN HUMAN LIFE

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Abstract: The increasing presence of the Internet in our everyday life raises important questions about what it means for access to resources, social interaction, and commitment to local community. This special issue of the American Behavioral Scientist brings together seven U.S., one U.K., one Canadian, and one North American study that examine the way in which the Internet competes with and complements everyday life. These studies show the Internet as a complex landscape of applications, purposes, and users. This introduction summarizes results from studies in this issue and other extant recent surveys, providing an overview of the Internet population and its activities, statistics that help define and articulate the nature of the digital divide. The authors move from there to consideration of the social consequences of adding Internet activity to our daily lives, exploring how use of the Internet affects traditional social and communal behaviors such as communication with local family and commitment to geographical communities. They conclude with a look at how these studies reveal the integration of the Internet into our everyday lives.

Keywords: Internet, Social Network, Cyberbullying, Cyber racism, Internet Addiction, Internet Risks, Online scams

Introduction: The Internet has become an integral part of modern man's daily life. With its help, you can always find the necessary information, make a video call at any time, and make payments for various services. Thanks to the Internet, there are almost unlimited possibilities in all areas of life. Internet plays an important role in our life. But it cannot be called good or bad. In this regard, you can metaphorically compare the Internet to a kitchen knife. You can use it to make delicious food. Or you can kill a person. And everyone makes his own choice, he is responsible for its consequences. The Internet in human life is good or bad depending on the individual. After all, if he chooses addiction or health damage - in the future he will have to "pay the bills" on his own. Those who use the Internet for good see its positive side. The Internet has many advantages:

The Internet is a great storehouse of information. Everyone can refer to their resources and find answers to their questions. Encyclopedias and reference books are a thing of the past. Now you can find the answer to every question on the Internet. Almost unlimited opportunities for communication. A person can communicate in social networks, messengers, find friends with the same interests. In the life of a teenager, the Internet has become the most important way to share your inner world with others. On the Internet, you can consult with a specialist, express your opinion and communicate. You can enjoy listening to music, viewing pictures, playing games. You can also find a job. [Designers](#), programmers and many other people can make money online. You can advertise your product online. The Internet is a great place for businessmen to advertise their products and find new customers. You can also list the weaknesses of the Internet: Uncontrolled arrangement of different information has led to confusion of factual information with unreliable information. For young people who are just beginning to absorb information, this leads to distorted ideas about the world. In addition to ordinary people, fraudsters, maniacs and other people with illegal intentions work in social networks. The Internet has become a real source of danger in our lives. In the conditions of freedom, sites of asocial nature have increased. Their bosses are factions, extremist groups. They promote violence and aggression. This group includes sites with pornographic content that has a negative effect on the child's psyche. The free posting of comments on the Internet has made profanity ubiquitous. Oaths of apparent anonymity have become the norm. The existence of games has become a disaster like computer addiction. Gambling addiction is like drug addiction. The opportunity to get a "new life" became for players to destroy the border between virtual life and reality. Posting photos on social networks has become one of the most dangerous types of Internet addiction. Teenagers who try to get a rare hit due to their stupidity often put their lives at risk. How do you understand Ideological Pressure?

Ideological immunity - various harm to the individual, social group, nation, society ideological and theoretical views that serve to protect against ideological influences and value system. Immunity (lat. immunitaq - freedom, escape) is a medical concept and maintaining the permanent internal identity of the organism, protecting itself from various influences, a set of reactions capable of protecting against the introduction of external infections understood. Simply put, immunity is the protection of the human body [against various diseases](#) is the ability to do. In contrast to the above, the general immunity of a person if the system is innate, it is necessary to develop ideological immunity. Secondly, it has its own characteristics for each generation. Third, the immune system it is possible to ensure ideological integrity in society only when it is formed. Ideological The main and first element of the immune system is knowledge. But, the type of knowledge " a lot.

Supporters of great state chauvinism or aggressive nationalism ideology they also rely on certain "knowledge", of course. Hence, ideological immunity knowledge in the system should be objective, accurately and fully reflect reality, a person should enrich its spirituality and serve the development of society. They are according to the essence, the interests of the Motherland and the nation should [be inextricably linked](#) need. The second key element of the ideological immune system is thus advanced. It is a system of values and values formed at the base of knowledge. After all, knowledge the more objective and deep it is, the values that have arisen at its core it will be so strong. In a word, the value system is ideological immunity determines the possibilities and is a strong shield against harmful ideas serves. But the very existence of a system of knowledge and values is ideological cannot fully express the essence of immunity. After all, these two elements are ideological. The third important element of immunity depends on the system of goals in the socio-economic, political and cultural-educational spheres. Such a system of specific goals if not, a person, nation or society is sometimes overtly or secretly ideological will be subjected to pressures.

Main body.

Today the world is changing rapidly. It's a panic of atoms, a factor trembling from the new methods of aggression and aggression being instilled with is standing. It is a mass destruction that humanity has arranged in the sky and on the ground with its mind and hands. The fear of weapons, the terrorist activities that are being carried out around us, are powerful intervention of states in the internal affairs of independent states, influential international political and economic pressure by organizations for their own benefit striving for the national interests of others, violence, political pressure transfers have become routine and various ideological attacks are being organized. Nowadays, the concepts of ideology and democracy are broad processes, philosophers and intellectuals interpret it in different terms. Ideology is philosophical as a category of a certain social group or nation, party and state philosophical, political, theoretically justifying and protecting fundamental interests refers to a whole system of legal, religious, spiritual and educational views. So, the national ideology of the Uzbek people is the theoretical and scientific fundamental interests of our nation foundational and protective philosophical, legal, political, spiritual, educational, religious is a whole system of views. The existence of each person is reflected in his ideology is enough. But ideology cannot be seen or grasped. This means that the ideology is dry a concept, not an abstract idea. Ideology is a clear, always perceptible, human being goals that encourage activity and give it spiritual and ideological power.

All the achievements of mankind during the long historical development, the world and self-awareness, individual intelligence, awareness and perception through this ideology will be available. Humanity without ideology is thrown from the ocean of humanity into the desert thrown away. Without ideology, neither the society, nor the

state, nor the person can take a step forward can't walk What humanity has lost in its history is ideologically is the result of poverty. All the riches he has achieved in his history, the basis of discoveries is ideology. The divine power of ideology is that good deeds, noble virtues, sacred values and beautiful traditions as a weapon of thought only when he becomes a strong defender of every person and every nation becomes That is why ideology is more powerful than any weapon. Independence In 2010, a great deal of incomparable work was done in the formation of the national ideology of the society increased. Our national values, traditions, historical traditions are sacred pilgrimage

Why is Physics important?

When it comes to physics, formulas and laws appear before our eyes. The existence surrounding us, their essence and movement are directly related to physics.

- In order to know how the world around us is structured, first of all, it is necessary to study the laws of physics, which are its basis, - says Physics, it does not consist only of complex formulas. It is reflected in every object before our eyes. Physics is the science of nature. He studies all phenomena and processes occurring in nature. Therefore, physics cannot be imagined separately from life. We live with physics every second. Gadgets that have become an integral part of our life, machines and technical tools that lighten our burden are, first of all, a product of physics. Every person will encounter physics during his life whether he wants it or not. But it is true that it is considered a relatively complex science. In fact, physics is the most interesting field, and at the same time, it opens the way for the development of industries that are the basis for the development of any country.

There is no easy knowledge in this life. Each subject has its own difficulty. It is true that science textbooks are complicated. In this regard, it would be appropriate to simplify some aspects. Teaching physics at school starts from the 6th grade. In my opinion, it would be appropriate to introduce students to simple concepts and definitions of physics starting from the lower grades. If we observe foreign experience, our textbooks are much simpler compared to foreign textbooks. The topics of the textbook prepared for the 7th grade correspond to the textbooks of our graduating class. These days, we are working on the translation of the 7th grade physics textbook developed at Cambridge University in cooperation with the Presidential Educational Institutions Agency. This textbook consists of 4 books and includes not only the general textbook, but also practical exercises and laboratory exercise books. Every achievement and discovery in the field of physics directly serves the development of mankind. The development of physics affects the level of development of industries important for production, economy, and development of the country as a whole. For example, after a certain discovery in physics is made, specialists who are involved in its application to production come to the field and create equipment that eases the burden of humanity. Discoveries in the field of atomic and nuclear physics made it

possible to use atomic energy. The discovery of semiconductors led to important changes in electronic computing. The exploitation of space allowed the transmission of data from any corner of the world, and the discovery of laser beams made it possible to use them in technology and health care. In short, the place of physics in human life is extremely incomparable.

Conclusion.

In recent years, attention has been increasingly paid to the quality of education. The increase in the quality of education depends on the teacher on the one hand, and on the students on the other hand. In improving the quality of education in physics, much attention should be paid to laboratory activities. For many years, science remained only a theory. This caused physics to be considered one of the most complex sciences. But if the acquired theoretical knowledge is tested in a laboratory exercise, both the level of recall increases and the interest of students increases. Today, all schools in the republic are not equipped with laboratory equipment at the same level. In this regard, programs are being developed that allow conducting virtual laboratories. The use of such programs should be expanded. Only then does physics not only consist of complex theories and rules that remain on paper.

In today's rapidly changing world, the demand for physics is increasing day by day, not decreasing. Because the industries that are important for the development of the country are developed with the help of natural sciences.

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